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Patient Beliefs and Behaviors on Online Information Use and Choice of Orthopedic Surgeon

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Abstract

Background: Due to increased patient choice, patient attitudes and behavior are important to understand. Few studies have examined the trustworthiness of online information and how it affects surgeon selection. This study examined patient attitudes and behavior toward online information and orthopedic surgeon choices. Secondary goals included understanding provider selection characteristics and their relationship to patient age and education.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study included five orthopedic surgery groups from various specialties. 165 orthopedic surgery patients received a 25-item questionnaire. Patients were asked to answer the questionnaire anonymously. Six questions assessed patient attitudes and behaviors toward online information, ten asked patients to rate the importance of orthopedic surgeon selection criteria on a 4-point Likert scale, and four asked about demographics.

Results: Emergency room (15/165, 8.8%), friend (21/165, 12.8%), insurance company (24/165 14.3%), internet search/website (14/165, 8.5%), primary care physician (74/165, 45.0%), and other are patient-reported referral sources. Before their initial appointment, 65 (39.5%) of 165 patients searched the Internet. Younger age groups believed internet material was more accurate and complete ($P=.02$). Younger groups were more likely to view physician rating websites as unbiased ($P=.003$), provide sufficient patient satisfaction information ($P=.01$), and provide physician education and training information ($P=.03$). A significant trend ($P<.001$) showed that younger patients were more likely to find a surgeon's website useful.

Conclusions: According to this study, patients place more weight on insurance networks, doctor recommendations, office locations, and appointment availability than they do on advertisements or online patient reviews, which are seen to be less beneficial when selecting an orthopedic surgeon. Future research can look into barriers that patients have when incorporating Internet resources for decision-making and techniques to enhance their health-seeking activities.

Keywords: Orthopedics, Practice Management, Social Media

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Introduction

The World Health Organization and the Institute of Medicine both define health literacy as a complex concept that includes social and cognitive skill sets that are distilled through patient experiences and are required to obtain, comprehend, and apply information to make appropriate health decisions (1,2). Healthcare organizations have emphasized that health literacy is crucial to patient-centered care. As a result, a large body of research examined trends in healthcare consumerism and developed characteristics that influence decisions about healthcare (3,4).

With the increased usage of social media and physician rating websites (PRWs), it is hypothesized that online tools and information may disrupt traditional patient-physician relationships as well as established measures of health care assessment. The most popular places for patients to find information about doctors and their practices are online review sites, social media platforms, and physician websites (5). Prior research aimed to categorize the data that patients posted online and look into how they behaved when they were online. Because healthcare incentives are not aligned as they are in other consumer industries, issues regarding the malignment of consumer happiness and quality have been raised. The rating scales on PRWs were shown to be erroneous and to have severe limitations. Approximately 59% of US participants expressed the opinion that PRW information is either somewhat or extremely essential, notwithstanding the established discrepancy between traditional quality measurements and user-generated internet evaluations (6). Therefore, it is yet unknown why patients use these platforms and whether or not their conduct is influenced by this information (7). Patients who are uninformed or wear uniforms have serious consequences. Poor patient outcomes, lower patient satisfaction, and more expenses have all been linked to insufficient health literacy. A distinct type of health literacy and a more advanced skill set are needed in orthopedic surgery to make well-informed judgments (8).

The goal of this study was to identify the internet sites patients use to investigate orthopedic surgeons and assess their value. We also examined demographic variables that may affect internet website use and the impact of other factors in choosing an orthopedic specialist. This study examined patient perceptions and behavior regarding online information and orthopedic surgeon referrals. Secondary aims included describing provider selection parameters' relative relevance and their relationship to patient age and education.

Materials and Methods

We conducted a cross-sectional study among patients in Diyarbakir orthopedic offices. Six orthopedic surgeon practices that screen patients in their clinics were part of the study group. Sports medicine, hand, spine, and foot and ankle subspecialties were among them. Patients who visited the clinics over three months filled out the surveys. Before taking part, each patient gave their consent. There were no identifiers associated with any specific responses, and the poll was anonymous and confidential. Every participant filled out the survey.

The seven survey questions were designed to identify patient behavior and assess patient opinion (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Survey of the study.

Please answer the questions below and return this sheet to the medical assistant or resident physician. Thank you for your participation.

1. What is your age?

18-25 26-35 36-45 46-55 56-65 66-75 76-85 85+

2. Please indicate the level of education you have completed:

Elementary/Middle School High School Some College Bachelor's Degree Masters Degree
 Doctorate Degree

3. How often do you use the internet?

Daily 4-5 times/week 2-3 times/week weekly

4. How important to you are the following when choosing an orthopedic specialist?

	Not Important 1	Slightly Important 2	Moderately Important 3	Very Important 4
Medical Knowledge	☐	☐	☐	☐
Surgical Skill	☐	☐	☐	☐
Bedside Manner	☐	☐	☐	☐
Insurance Network Compatibility	☐	☐	☐	☐
Out-of-Pocket Cost	☐	☐	☐	☐
Availability	☐	☐	☐	☐
Word of Mouth Referrals from Friends/Family	☐	☐	☐	☐
Recommendations from Other Physicians	☐	☐	☐	☐
Internet Reviews by Patients	☐	☐	☐	☐
Institution where Surgeon's Training was Completed	☐	☐	☐	☐
TV/Print/Other Advertising	☐	☐	☐	☐

5. Please indicate any/all websites you have used to obtain information on the orthopedic specialist you are seeing today:

doktorum.com doktorsitesi.com doktortakvimi.com Facebook.com
 WebMD.com evital.com trdoktor.com doktorumonline.net
 Twitter.com Website of office/surgical group Surgeon's website

6. Do you feel Patient Satisfaction is equivalent to a successful treatment outcome?

Yes No

7. Do you feel that websites offering patient reviews regarding orthopedic surgeons provide information on the following:

Accurate/complete information on the surgeon and practice Yes No
 Unbiased Reviews Yes No
 Treatment Complication Rates Yes No

Ongoing or Previous Litigation Claims Yes No
 Data regarding Patient Satisfaction Yes No

Patients were asked to report their demographics, actions, and attitudes in the survey. The patient's age, degree of education, and frequency of internet use were all recorded in three questions. In one inquiry, patients were asked to rank particular factors for selecting orthopedic surgeons on a 4-point Likert scale, where 1 meant "not important" and 4 meant "very important." Patients were asked two questions on online patient reviews and whether or not patient satisfaction corresponds with a successful course of treatment. Before their clinic visit, the patient's use of websites was evaluated by one inquiry. The surveys were filled out in person by the participants, and their answers were kept confidential. Notably, the survey is a survey of questions rather than a validated questionnaire measuring a particular result. The findings of the descriptive analysis of the responses to an exploratory study on patient behaviors, beliefs, and trends are presented in this paper.

The age ranges of the respondents were as follows: 18–25, 26–35, 36–45, 46–55, 56–65, and 76–85 years. The greatest level of education attained by the respondents—elementary/middle school, high school, some college, bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees—was used to stratify the population. When distributing the survey, a qualified research assistant or medical assistant gave the participants an explanation for each question. MedCalc software was used to evaluate basic descriptive statistics. Kendall τ was utilized to investigate relationships, while the median was used to represent central tendency and frequencies for ordinal Likert-scale data. Correlation coefficients with precision estimates (95% CI) are used to report associations. For the analysis of categorical variables, the Cochran-Armitage test was employed, as it is thought to be more effective than the χ^2 test in determining trends in proportions and frequencies. The cutoff point for statistical significance was determined at $P < .05$.

Results

The survey was completed by all 165 patients who were given it during July and August of 2023. Based on the orthopedic surgeon's specialization they were consulting, Table 2 shows the distribution of patients who responded to the survey. Most patients (114/165, 69.0%) reported using the internet every day at baseline. Next were 2-3 times a week (12/165, 7.0%) and 4-5 times a week (10/165, 6.5%).

Table 2: Participants' orthopedic subspecialty

Subspecialty	Patients, n (%)
Spine	75 (46.3)
Sport	59 (36.7)
Hand	17 (10.2)
Foot and ankle	11 (6.8)

The emergency room (15/165, 8.8%), friends (21/165, 12.8%), insurance company (24/165, 14.3%), internet search/website (14/165, 8.5%), primary care physician (PCP; 74/165, 45.0%), and other (17/165, 10.3%) were the sources of referrals as indicated by the patients. Sixty-five (39.5%) of the 165 patients said they had looked up the surgeon online before their initial appointment. The websites of the surgeon (32/65, 48.5%) and the office/surgical group (18/65, 26.9%) were accessed by the majority of these patients. The office location ($P = .05$), doctor suggestion ($P < .001$), online reviews ($P < .001$), and advertising sources ($P = .01$) were all substantially correlated with patient age. Out-of-pocket expenses ($P = .05$), availability ($P < .001$), office location ($P < .001$), online appointment scheduling ($P = .004$), surgeon training ($P = .002$), and advertisement sources ($P < .001$) were all substantially correlated with

the degree of patient education. Patients rated availability (92/165, 55.9%), insurance coverage (130/165, 79.0%), out-of-pocket expenses (108/165, 66.0%), and a referral from another doctor as "extremely important" (scoring of 4). 102 (62.0%) of the 165 patients gave the importance of surgeon advertising a 1 (not important). In each area, the percentage of times that internet reviews were considered significant varied from 21% to 29%. Of the 165 respondents, only 41 (24.9%) thought highly of the surgeon's training institution, and 49 (30%) thought it was moderately essential.

Patients who said they found the surgeon's website helpful did so most frequently. Out of all the factors asked about in the questionnaire, the least amount of patients said that the information found online is accurate and comprehensive. Regarding their perceptions of PRWs and online information, patient education groups did not significantly correlate with one another. In the younger age groups, there was a trend toward a greater belief in the accuracy and completeness of internet information ($P=.02$). Younger groups were more likely than older groups to believe that PRWs are objective ($P=.003$), that they provide enough information on patient satisfaction ($P=.01$), and that they provide information about medical education and training ($P=.03$). Patients who thought the surgeon's website was helpful also showed a significant trend ($P<.001$), with a higher relative frequency in younger age groups.

Discussion

Out of the 165 patients (8.5%) who responded to the survey, only 14 (or 28%) chose their orthopedic surgeon online by searching through websites. Interestingly, 103 (62.3%) patients were recommended to their orthopedic surgeon from sources associated with health care (emergency room, insurance company, and PCP). Of these, PCPs referred the greatest number of patients (74/165, 45.0%). 102 patients (62.0%) rated this feature as 1 (not important), which was consistent with the data's overall low importance of patient-oriented marketing. According to our data, patients are value-driven and consider out-of-pocket expenses (95/165, 57.4%) and insurance coverage (130/165, 79.0%) to be extremely significant factors. Out of the 165 patients, only 65 (39.5%) searched online before their initial appointment. Significant patterns were noted, including younger patient groups' perceptions of the accuracy and completeness of online information and their positive sentiments of PRWs' ability to provide adequate and objective information.

Our results show that patients do not actively participate in their care, even though the amount of internet information available to them is expanding quickly. This conclusion validates findings that have been reported before (9). Additionally, patients did not inquire about the medical expertise of the practitioner, legal matters, or patient happiness. It was suggested that patient satisfaction could serve as a proxy for quality of care due to the intricate relationships between social, demographic, cultural, and cognitive factors that affect satisfaction. The multifaceted evaluation of quality was abandoned and judged unsuitable. According to Rothenfluh et al. (10), patients' decisions differ when it comes to choosing a hotel and a provider because they have less faith in the accuracy of online information about doctors. This could be because they believe it is impossible to evaluate a physician's quality, even when it is based on information that is readily available online. However, we discovered that 40% of patients used online resources to research topics before their clinic visit, while only 24% of patients who visited an outpatient orthopedic clinic in 2002 reported doing so. The integration of online information is probably not being used as much as it could be, and future studies should aim to identify the underlying causes or obstacles (11).

Surgeons should prioritize their contacts with community physician referral sources, according to our research. A prior study on referrals to plastic surgeons brought this to light, demonstrating that 82% of patients thought a referral from another doctor was extremely essential to somewhat important—a statistically significant finding across all age categories (12). The insurance network and referrals from friends, family, and doctors were found to be significant determinants in the selection of a foot and ankle surgeon. These factors are corroborated by

our data as significant determinants of patient decision-making. It is also possible to examine the external validity of the results among investigations. Important considerations for patients choosing their total joint replacement surgeon and facility were rated on a 5-point Likert scale in a different study (13). Professional reputation is important, according to all three of the aforementioned reports. In a similar vein, women's choices of obstetrician/gynecologist were greatly influenced by referrals from other medical professionals and insurance providers (14). Future research should assess whether patients' decisions about primary care versus urgent/emergent care referrals, and the opinions of other orthopedic surgeons, and other community medical professionals differ.

The study's correlation patterns were unexpected and deserving of notice. It has been shown that age and educational attainment have an impact on health literacy, with graduate-degree holders 130 times more likely to have sufficient health literacy ($P=.01$). With a relative risk of 1.40, less than college education is an independent predictor of low musculoskeletal health literacy. Several statistically significant relationships with nonconsequential impact sizes were shown by our data. It's important to note that previous research has shown a significant positive correlation between younger age and both higher usage and perceived usefulness of internet information (15,16).

There were certain restrictions with this survey. A small, convenient sample of people was given the survey. As a result, even though the trial was anonymously available to all patients at a sizable private clinic, the sample size of participants was underpowered. Similarly, it is impossible to determine whether our sample has a bias in selection. The absence of a comparison group, which increases sampling bias, is another serious problem. Since our survey lacks standardization and validation, response bias might have crept in. However, our objective was not to infer a causal mechanism but to characterize a macroscopic phenomenon.

Conclusions

According to this study, patients place more weight on insurance networks, doctor recommendations, office locations, and appointment availability than they do on advertisements or online patient reviews when selecting an orthopedic surgeon. Our findings contradict widely held beliefs about patient agency and consumer autonomy in healthcare. Future research can look into barriers that patients have when incorporating Internet resources for decision-making and techniques to enhance their health-seeking activities.

Declaration of interest:

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

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Informed consent:

Written informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Contributions

Research concept and design: **EÖ**

Data analysis and interpretation: **EÖ**

Collection and/or assembly of data: **EÖ**

Writing the article: **EÖ**

Critical revision of the article: **EÖ**

Final approval of the article: **EÖ**

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